

Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards in Rare Hematological Diseases

Deliverable 1.2

Data Management Plan

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Table of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ACL	Access Control List
ATHENA	Analysis of Tumor Heterogeneity in Spatial Omics Measurements
CING	Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics
CSV	comma-separated values
DAC	Data Access Control
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EJP RD	European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases
ERDRI	European Rare Disease Registry Infrastructure
EU	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
OMOP-CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model
ORDO	Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology
PDF	Portable Document Format
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measures
RHD	Rare Haematological Disease
STSE	Short-Term Staff Exchange

1. Executive summary

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are key elements of good data management. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an initial DMP that describes which data will be generated and reused in the HemaFAIR project and plan how to organize, document, store, preserve, and share them, in line with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles and any other applicable ethical and legal requirements. The DMP is written to ensure the quality, longevity, and reusability of the project's research data during and by the end of the project. The plan will be revised and updated twice throughout the project. In the next version, tools like vu.nl or ds.wizard that are designed to assist writing of DMPs will be considered.

The main datasets that will be generated/reused through the project and considered in this deliverable are:

- Personal patient data and special categories of data (e.g., health and generic data)
- Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) data
- Personal data (from project partners, dissemination audience)
- Research output and publication data

2. Introduction

The research component of the HemaFAIR project aims to demonstrate a 'FAIRification' (i.e., making data and metadata more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) method on one national (Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry) and one international (INHERENT – International Hemoglobinopathy Research Network) project/data collection. As part of the project, patient data (including personal, clinical, and medical history data) will be processed. PROM instruments will be developed, and PROM responses will be collected from >100 hemoglobinopathy patients in Cyprus on the REDCap data platform.

As part of dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) activities, HemaFAIR will also involve the collection of personal data from the project's stakeholders. Surveys and questionnaires will be used to map the stakeholder's training needs in order to develop the training materials accordingly. Similarly, personal data will also be collected by using surveys and interviews from the partners throughout the project for communication and organizational purposes to assess the types of training activities they can offer to CING and other stakeholders in Cyprus. Some examples of DEC activities that will involve the collection of personal data are from researchers involved in short-term staff exchange (STSE) programmes, mentoring programmes, or other stakeholders who are interested in attending the events of the HemaFAIR project.

This deliverable summarises the proposed approach for a DMP, which focuses specifically on the management of patient data that will be collected/reused during the project and additionally, on personal data that will be collected from all involved stakeholders as well as the research output data of the project. The DMP is presented based on the preliminary understanding of the project's data requirements. This deliverable is the first version and will be revised and updated in M18 (D2.1) and M36 (D2.2). The following sections are based on the DMP template provided by the European Commission (EU) for Horizon Europe projects.

3. Data Summary

Aspect	Explanation of patient data collected/processed as part of the use case (patient generic, health data, and PROMs)	Explanation of personal data collected as part of surveys and questionnaires for DEC activities and other project data
Any re-use of existing data and how this will be done	<p>The Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry and the International Hemoglobinopathy Research Network contain demographics, clinical, laboratory, treatment, and genetic data. Therefore, HemaFAIR will not collect any new patient data (generic, clinical, diagnostics, etc.). These data will be re-used as part of the HemaFAIR use case.</p> <p>As part of D13.1, FAIRified PROM module on Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry. Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) will be collected from adult hemoglobinopathy patients.</p> <p>The data processing will be carried out in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).</p>	Published project research output and dissemination materials i.e., research papers, lecture slides, conference materials, leaflets, newsletters, and other training materials can be accessed through a central repository and the HemaFAIR website.
Types and formats of data the project will generate/reuse	The project will reuse pseudonymized personal (health and generic) data from patients diagnosed with a hemoglobinopathy. Patient data will include demographics, clinical, diagnosis, genetic data,	The project will collect personal information from partners, event attendees, training programme attendees, and researchers involved in the project through surveys and questionnaires.

	<p>medical history, quality of life, and survival data. Newly generated PROMs will also be collected from adult hemoglobinopathy patients through the REDCap platform.</p>	<p>Other types of data that will be generated are the dissemination materials such as newsletters, posters, publications, training materials (workshops, webinars, lectures)</p>
<p>Purpose of the data generation/reuse and its relation to the objectives of the project</p>	<p>Data collected from one national (Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry) and one international (International Hemoglobinopathy Research Network) platform (INHERENT) as well as the collection of >100 PROM responses from hemoglobinopathy patients in Cyprus, will be used in the FAIRification process and federated analysis as part of the HemaFAIR use case to facilitate data sharing when required. With these objectives: a) federated data analysis of FAIRified data in these two platforms and b) exchange and integration of FAIRified data between them will be demonstrated</p>	<p>Personal data will be collected for coordination of DEC activities, to identify the knowledge and skill gaps at CING, and Cyprus. Personal data from partner institutes will be collected to understand the training capabilities they can offer to CING.</p> <p>Publications and training materials will be generated as part of the dissemination activities of the project research output on improving the knowledge of FAIR principles usage for the management of data.</p>
<p>The origin of the data</p>	<p>Cyprus Haemoglobinopathy Patient Registry, INHERENT, PROMs</p>	<p>Surveys, questionnaires, event forms</p>
<p>Expected size of the data</p>	<p>< 1GB.</p>	
<p>Likely users of the data</p>	<p>The Consortium partners will not have direct access to the patient data. If necessary, they will have access to fully anonymized patient data.</p>	<p>The dissemination data will also be publicly available in a trusted research repository such as Zenodo. Repository information and access links to the dissemination data will be provided on the project's website.</p>

4. FAIR Data

4.1 Making data findable

Aspect	Explanation of patient data collected/processed as part of the use case (patient generic, health data, and PROMs)	Explanation of personal data collected as part of surveys and questionnaires for DEC activities and other project data
Identification of data by a persistent identifier	All contributions to the project's datasets will be uniquely identifiable and the data will be uniquely attributable through unique identifiers provided by initiatives like ORCID, and DataCite respectively.	<p>Regarding research publication data, where possible, the FAIR Principles will be followed and Open Access publications will be provided. The Consortium will consider the use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI). The consortium will ensure, at the latest, at the time of the publication, that a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a trusted repository.</p> <p>Training materials will be collected and deposited in a repository for reusability and long-term availability. Workshop and conference materials will be provided with Open Access using e.g., Zenodo.</p>
Rich metadata to be provided to allow discovery	For the data already collected on the Cyprus patient registry and the PROMs that will be collected as part of this project, this will be provided in accordance with the ERDRI Central Metadata Repository (ERDRI.mdr) and through publications.	
Type of metadata that will be created and the disciplinary or	The Consortium will agree on the most appropriate standard depending on the feasibility of making an	

general standards that will be followed	anonymous data set available for reuse. For the patient data, ERDRI contains a collection of metadata, which specifies the used data elements of a registry including the designation of the used data elements, their definition, and units of measurement.	
Any search keywords to be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use	The patient dataset will be discoverable through ERDRI where a collection of metadata and search keywords is provided.	
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	INHERENT and Cyprus patient registry will share metadata in EDRDI.mdr	

Table 1 Making data findable

4.2 Making data accessible

Aspect	Explanation of patient data collected/processed as part of the use case (patient generic, health data, and PROMs)	Explanation of personal data collected as part of surveys and questionnaires for DEC activities and other project data
Repository Aspects		
Trusted repository (Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository? Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?)	Patient data will not be made available through a repository	Publications of research output will be openly accessible and available on Zenodo.
Does the repository ensure that the	The chosen repository (Zenodo) ensures that the data is assigned a digital objective identifier (DOI)	

<p>data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</p>		
Data Aspects		
<p>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement</p>	<p>Patient data will not be openly available in order to remain in compliance with European and national data protection laws. Anonymized and aggregated data will be shared internally in the Consortium, whenever needed, considering the use of ACLs.</p> <p>The access to PROMs will be based on the data access control (DAC) that will be defined in the REDCap platform.</p>	<p>Pre-publication versions of the publications and paper presentations will be released through the project website and project's Zenodo account. Social media channels will be used to provide links to publications and presentation files.</p>
<p>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g., patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</p>	<p>The Consortium will define precise rules for the reusability of patient data: Licenses for data sharing and re-use (Creative Commons, Open Data Commons). This will be confirmed and updated in the next versions of DMP (in the revised deliverables D2.1 and D2.2).</p>	

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol? If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	During the project, the coordinator (CING) will not provide access to patient data for the Consortium members. Only, if necessary, fully anonymized patient data will be accessible.	
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	No one from the consortium except the coordinator (CING) will have access to the patient data. In addition, if necessary, different access levels (as defined in REDCap) will be defined for the consortium, thus allowing granular access to different information depending on the user credentials and the consent provided by the patient.	Published research output will be openly accessible to the public.
Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g., to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	Not applicable	
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.	The metadata of the Cyprus patient registries and PROMs will be open, available, and discoverable through the ERDRI.mdr (Central Metadata Repository) where a collection of metadata and search keywords is provided.	The details for the metadata for any other project data, the DMP will be updated in the revised deliverable D2.1.
Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	ERDRI.mdr contains a collection of metadata that specify the used data elements of a registry including the designation of the used data elements, their definition, and units of measurement.	

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	The data will remain available for the whole duration of the project. It will be decided at a later point and updated in the next versions of DMP (in the revised deliverables D.2.1 and D2.2), which data and metadata will remain available and findable and for how long after the end of the project under what restrictions after the end of the project.	
Will documentation or references about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open-source code)?	Aggregated patient data will be able to be exported through REDCap and will be accessible with open-source tools. In addition, open-source tools such as R, Python, and Highcharts will be used to generate statistical data, visualizations and interactive graphs.	In general, all the project data will be exported in available formats i.e. .csv, .pdf, such as no special software is needed to read or open them.

Table 2 Making data accessible

4.3 Making data interoperable

Aspect	Explanation of patient data collected/processed as part of the use case (patient generic, health data, and PROMs)	Explanation of personal data collected as part of surveys and questionnaires for DEC activities and other project data
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats, or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and reuse within and across disciplines?	Standards and state-of-the-art tools such as ERDRI.mdr will be used. In addition, standard ontologies according to EU recommendations, such as ORDO, SNOMED-CT, HPO, and LOINC, will be used to make patient data interoperable.	
Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	The current data model for the two platforms will be aligned with the semantically rich common data model promoted by the EJP RD/ERDERA and ensure interoperability with widely adopted models such as OMOP-CDM using tools such as ATHENA. The exact tools to be used will be	

	determined later in the project.	
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?	We do not anticipate the need to adopt uncommon ontologies or vocabularies.	
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g., other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	If needed throughout the project, the project data will include qualified references to other (meta)data.	

Table 3 Making data interoperable

4.4 Increase data re-use

Aspect	Explanation for all the patient data collected/processed in the project	Explanation of personal data collected as part of surveys and questionnaires for DEC activities and other project data
Documentation to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use	Readme files including all the necessary information will be added as documentation.	
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Patient-level data will be unavailable both to the consortium and to the public. Aggregated patient data and other research output data will be stored in a repository i.e., Github, for reproducibility that permits the licensing of the data.	
Data licensing using standard reuse licences, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement	The type of license will be determined later in the project and confirmed in the next versions of DMP (in the revised deliverables D2.1 and D2.2)	

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The consortium will discuss whether or not the data produced in the project will be useable by third parties and this information will be updated in the next versions of DMP (in the revised deliverables D2.1 and D2.2)	
Documentation of the provenance of the data using the appropriate standards.	REDCap platform maintains a built-in audit trail that logs all user activity and all pages viewed by every user, including contextual information (the project or record being accessed)	
All relevant data quality assurance processes.	REDCap platform contains already defined data quality checks and reports can be exported to monitor the data quality.	

Table 4 Increasing data re-use

5. Other research outputs

This will be determined later in the project and updated in the next versions of DMP.

6. Allocation of resources

Aspect	Response/explanation
Estimated project costs for making data FAIR and how these will be covered.	This will be determined later once the feasibility of sharing is confirmed by the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and Compliance processes and will be considered as part of the feasibility of developing an accessible data set.
Data management responsibility across the project.	The coordinator will take lead responsibility for the management of the patient data and all other project data i.e., publications and dissemination material.
Resources required for long-term preservation (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long).	To be determined later in the project, under the responsibility of the coordinator. This would include a sustainability business model for datasets that will be made available for open access, covering costs of long-term storage, the maintenance of the data sets if necessary, and any human resources required to manage data sharing assuming the development of this data set is feasible.

Table 5 Allocation of resources

7. Data Security

Aspect	Response for the patient data
<p>Data security provisions (including data recovery as well as secure storage / archiving and transfer of sensitive data)</p>	<p>All patient data are stored in local servers (including backup servers) at CING. Additional security measures are already implemented for all the patient data, to ensure the protection of data, based on internationally established best practices. These measures will also be continuously maintained and adapted to support the long-term curation and preservation of the data. Specifically, security measures are ensured at four different levels (a) network security, through the use of firewalls and secured data communication and daily backups of the database on separate servers, (b) physical security at the hosting site of the databases and platform, and (c) software security through the use of ACLs.</p>
<p>Trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation</p>	<p>Patient data are stored in local servers (including backup servers) at CING. The GitHub repository will also be used to store aggregated patient data and other research outputs, ensuring long-term preservation and curation. To maintain data processing integrity, version control and comprehensive metadata standards will be employed, enabling clear documentation of data provenance and updates. For reusability, the data will be formatted in open, widely accepted standards (e.g., CSV, JSON), accompanied by detailed documentation (readme files), data dictionaries, and licenses (e.g., CC BY 4.0) to facilitate clear terms of use. Security will be ensured through access control measures, such as authenticated user permissions.</p>

Table 6 Data security

8. Ethics

Aspect	Response/explanation for all patient data
Any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing	For the patient data, pseudonymized patient-level data will be shared only through the Consortium only if necessary. In general, there are potential local research ethics / independent review board prohibitions and data protection issues, which we will examine carefully before determining which other project output data can be made available as open research data.
Questionnaires dealing with personal data of project partners	Only internally for the Consortium, otherwise, patients and participants will not be approached.
How is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in such questionnaires?	The patients whose data will be collected and/or re-used will have to sign an informed consent document and provide their consents about re-using their data for research purposes and for entering their data into the database.

Table 7 Ethics

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, the HemaFAIR project acknowledges the vital importance of strong data management practices to ensure the integrity, accessibility, and security of research data. A comprehensive DMP has been created to guide the Consortium throughout the project's duration.

Our dedication to data management is a core principle that is essential to achieving our research goals. By implementing the strategies outlined in this DMP, we aim to accomplish the following:

- **Data Integrity:** We will uphold the highest standards of data quality and consistency, ensuring that the data generated within the project are reliable and trustworthy.
- **Data Accessibility:** We will endeavor to make our research data as accessible as possible, promoting transparency and driving scientific progress.
- **Data Security:** We will enforce rigorous security measures to protect sensitive and confidential data, safeguarding individual privacy and adhering to ethical standards.
- **Collaboration:** Effective data management will enable smooth collaboration among consortium members and boost the project's overall productivity.
- **Long-Term Impact:** We understand that the benefits of our research will extend beyond the project's timeline. As such, we are committed to preserving and sharing data to support future research and innovation.

Data management is a dynamic process that requires ongoing evaluation and adaptation. Our DMP will act as a living document, subject to regular reviews and updates to meet the evolving needs and challenges of the HemaFAIR project.